

Education Quarterly Reviews

Baslini; Sasongko, Rambat Nur; Kristiawan, Muhammad; And Walid, Ahmad (2021), The Effect of the Implementation of the English Subject Teacher Deliberative Policy on Learning Management in Realizing Teacher Performance. In: *Education Quarterly Reviews*, Vol.4, No.2, 69-73.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.04.02.197

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Education Quarterly Reviews* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Education Quarterly Reviews* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of education, linguistics, literature, educational theory, research, and methodologies, curriculum, elementary and secondary education, higher education, foreign language education, teaching and learning, teacher education, education of special groups, and other fields of study related to education. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Education Quarterly Reviews* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of education.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

Teacher Deliberative Policy on Learning Management in Realizing Teacher's Performance

Baslini¹, Rambat Nur Sasongko², Muhammad Kristiawan³, Ahmad Walid⁴

¹ Sekolah Menengah Atas Negeri 4 Lahat, Sumatera Selatan, Indonesia. Email: baslini.pga@gmail.com

² Universitas Bengkulu, Indonesia. Email: rambatnursasongko@unib.ac.id

³ Universitas Bengkulu, Indonesia. Email: muhammadkristiawan@unib.ac.id

⁴ Institut Agama Islam Negeri Bengkulu, Indonesia. Email: ahmadwalid@iainbengkulu.ac.id

Correspondence: Baslini, Sekolah Menengah Atas Negeri 4 Lahat, Sumatera Selatan, Indonesia.
Email: baslini.pga@gmail.com

Abstract

The purpose of writing this article is to discuss the effect of implementing the subject teacher deliberation policy on the management of English learning in realizing the performance of English teachers in the subject teacher deliberation forum which is under the auspices of the South Sumatra Provincial Education Office. The method of analysis in the discussion of this main topic uses an effectual causal analysis model by reviewing the rational relationship that analyzes the causal relationship between the implementation of subject teacher deliberation policy, English language learning management and the performance of English teachers. The location of the research was carried out in the subject teacher deliberation forum under the auspices of the Education Office of South Sumatra Province with a total of 88 respondents. This discussion shows that the implementation of the subject teacher deliberation policy has no significant effect on the management of English learning and the performance of English teachers. This article concludes that realizing the performance of English teachers can be done by optimizing the implementation of the subject teacher deliberation policy and management of English learning.

Keywords: Implementation, Teacher Performance, Management

1. Introduction

In line with the enactment of Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System on July 8, 2003 by the Government, this has resulted in policy changes within the authority of Indonesian National Education. Law Number 20 of 2003 automatically generates new provisions in the functions, goals and obligations of the government to realize quality education for the Indonesian nation. Based on this, the Government has scheduled three main policies in the field of education, namely: Expanding and equitable access to education; Improvement of quality, relevance and competitiveness; and Strengthening governance, accountability, and public image

At the level of expanding and equitable access to education, as stated by Law Number 20 of 2003, Chapter IV, Article 5 paragraphs (1) and (5) states that: every citizen has the same right to obtain quality education (paragraph 1); every citizen has the right to the opportunity to improve lifelong education (paragraph 5). Meanwhile, at the level of quality improvement and strengthening of governance, the government then issued Government Regulation Number 74 of 2008 concerning Teachers as the elaboration of Law Number 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers. Based on Government Regulation Number 74 of 2008, the government mandates that teachers must have a minimum academic qualification of S1 (strata 1) or D-IV, which is then supported by adequate competence and supported by an educator certificate. In order to support this, teachers are required to be able to always improve their abilities according to the development of science in a sustainable manner. In this connection, in order for the process of improving academic qualifications and teacher competence to be programmed and carried out properly, a forum for independent and professional teacher development is needed.

In general, the problem phenomena in this study are: The implementation of the Subject Teacher Deliberation policy has not been implemented properly. This can be seen from the implementation of the collaborative activities that have not been running optimally. These activities include, namely first, create and practice using learning tools / materials. second, bring in experts. third, practice using a new learning approach. And fourth and discuss the latest educational issues. The management of English learning has not been optimally implemented in the forum. One of the indications is that the English teachers have not shown their potential effectively and efficiently. This can be seen from the fact that there are still English teachers who have not made a mature and measured learning plan that is contained in the lesson plan. In addition, planning carried out in the teaching and learning process is not evaluated carefully and continuously, so that the shortcomings of the planning contained in the lesson plan cannot be followed up for improvement.

The performance of English teachers is not optimal, where the teachers do not master the four language skills in English which include: listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills. However, in the meantime the teachers have only mastered the linguistic aspects which include: aspects of grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation. Based on the explanation above, the constraints that affect the ineffectiveness of the program, among others, arise from the aspects of policy implementation, management, and performance. These three aspects have a causal relationship that requires further study. Based on this statement, the researcher determined a research topic with a title, "The Effect of Subject Teacher Deliberative Policy Implementation on English Learning Management in Realizing English Teacher Performance.

2. Methods

Research is the process of collecting, analyzing, and translating information and data systematically to increase understanding of a certain phenomenon (Nurlaeli & Saryono, 2018). The research uses the scientific method by collecting data and testing the analysis of the hypothesis (Nurlaeli & Saryono, 2018). The method used in this research is descriptive method of quantitative analysis with survey techniques. What is meant by descriptive research method is that it has something to do with the exposure of a phenomenon or a relationship between two or more phenomena (Thohir et al., 2019). The survey technique used in this research is a research method by taking a population by census using a questionnaire as a means of collecting basic data to study the observed phenomena or symptoms. The research approaches and techniques used in this study are expected to provide answers to the phenomena studied, namely regarding the variables of subject teacher deliberation policy implementation, English learning management and English teacher performance.

This research is an evaluation study of the implementation of public policy, where the implementation of public policy is defined as the implementation or application of a public policy through a program, activity, action, or action in a mechanism that is tied to a certain system (Ramdhani & Ramdhani, 2017). To strengthen the research results, verification of the research results was carried out with the results of observations, interviews, and literature studies as recommended by Ramdhani & Ramdhani (2104), and Ramdhani et al. (2014).

Respondents of this study were English teachers who joined the forum in Lahat Regency, with a population of 88 people. The discussion was carried out on the implementation of the subject teacher deliberation policy as an effort to improve the management of English learning in realizing the performance of English teachers.

3. Results and Discussion

The place for teacher coaching in question is the Subject Teacher Conference which is intended for teachers at school levels. Furthermore, the Subject Teacher Deliberation is understood as a forum for gathering similar subject teachers collaboratively in a certain area regency in order to identify and solve problems, test and develop new ideas in order to improve the quality of learning. So that the forum is believed to be one of the effective media to foster teacher professionalism within the framework of by-, from-, and- for teachers activities. In addition, is believed to be a means to improve teacher skills which include pedagogical, professional, social, and personal abilities (Jalal, 2005).

Because is a mandate of a Government Regulation, formally is included in the domain of public policy which must be implemented as well as possible in order to provide maximum benefits for the life of the nation and state (Winarno, 2016). However, in reality on the ground, the still collided with obstacles so that the had not been able to produce optimal teacher performance. The ineffectiveness of the performance of subject teachers, especially English teachers who are members of the , is caused by the lack of quality of work of the teachers involved in it. In addition, there are other aspects, such as: work speed / accuracy, work initiative, work ability, and communication (Uno & Lamatenggo, 2014).

Of the five aspects above, aspects of work quality and job ability are the main factors faced by English teachers. In practice, English teachers still tend not to be able to maximize their language skills which include language skills and language aspects. Language skills, including listening skills, speaking skills, reading skills, and writing skills. Meanwhile, the language aspect includes the ability to master grammar, the ability to master vocabulary, and the ability to master pronunciation.

Apart from the performance factor, the management aspect is also suspected to be a factor in the ineffectiveness of the performance of English teachers who are members of the forum. In an organization, the organizers and members involved can carry out optimal organizational management functions. In the context of English language learning management, English teachers are not only able to provide optimal performance, they are also required to carry out management functions related to English learning which ultimately lead to the achievement of predetermined goals through the use of human resources and resources. others (Winardi, 1998 in Iskandar, 2016). In management, the implementation of these management functions should include efforts to plan, organize, actuating, and control (Terry, in Iskandar, 2016).

Apart from management factors that can influence the success of performance aspects, factors in the implementation of government policies are also suspected to be a factor in the ineffectiveness of this performance. Basically, the implementation of the policy returns to the policy maker, namely the government, then carried out by the policy implementing agency, then the tools used in socializing the policy, and the public as the target of a policy.

In the context of public policies that specifically regulate education in Indonesia, which later gave birth to , the government initially issued Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System on July 8, 2003 which resulted in a change in policy within the authority of Indonesian National Education. Then Law Number 20 of 2003 was strengthened by Law Number 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers as executors of education policies that directly interact with the public at the school and college levels. Then to strengthen the professionalism of teachers, the Government issued Government Regulation Number 74 of 2008 concerning Teachers, so that the PP gave birth to 4 regulations which became the legal basis for the formation of the . The four regulations are outlined in: Signs for the development of activities, Standard operational procedures for the implementation of the ; Standard operational procedures for curriculum development at the educational unit level at the ; and development standards.

With this special regulation that regulates , the government hopes that can run well, so that it can optimally improve the performance of teachers, especially English teachers. So that education will be more dynamic, teaching will be more productive so that it has a satisfied effect on students, parents / guardians and the community as the targets of this public policy.

Based on the results of research and discussion of the effect of implementing the subject teacher deliberation policy on the management of English learning in realizing the performance of English teachers, the following conclusions and suggestions can be drawn:

First, in relation to the Subject Teacher Deliberative Policy Implementation variable, the following problems were found: Not all of the English teachers in the of Lahat Regency did not understand the meaning of the policies that had to be implemented. Based on the background of the problem in the Implementation of Subject Teacher Deliberative Policy, the authors suggest to the South Sumatra Provincial Education Office to increase the socialization of the Government's policy on the Subject Teacher Deliberation Program, especially for English Subjects which are carried out in school units Senior High School. This is important given the teachers' lack of awareness in their active involvement in the professional forum for these subject teachers. The steps that can be taken are by: Providing clearer and more detailed knowledge and understanding to teachers regarding the Subject Teacher Consultation policy, Increasing budget allocations for socialization so that activities are carried out according to set goals and Involving all levels of teachers, heads schools, and leadership elements in the Education and Culture Office in order to formulate programs / activities so that the involvement and ideas of all stakeholder elements can be accommodated.

Second, related to the English Learning Management variable, namely the following problems were found: the mapped objectives could not be implemented optimally, the monitoring of activities had not been carried out continuously, and supervision had not been able to provide improvement in teacher administration. Based on the background of the problems in English Learning Management, the authors suggest that the South Sumatra Provincial Education Office can increase the work motivation of teachers, school principals, and supervisors. The steps that can be taken are: Providing opportunities for teachers, school principals, and supervisors to get education, training and technical guidance related to their work, Encouraging teachers, especially English teachers to make work innovations in order to improve program outcomes in the future and increase cooperation, both inside and outside the work environment to strengthen relationships between teachers of other subjects.

Third, related to the English Teacher Performance variable, the following problems were found: not all English teachers have made plans for meeting teaching and learning activities that are in accordance with the academic calendar, not all English teachers who are members of the can provide an evaluation of the results of student work so that students can find out their weaknesses. and the lack of application of current teaching methods. Based on the background of the problems in the performance of English teachers, the authors suggest that the South Sumatra Provincial Education Office can improve the quality of their knowledge and skills to be able to provide excellent service to their students. The steps that can be taken include: Building a sense of empathy for English teachers through various self-development training, motivation and so on, Establishing teaching and learning standards as a service that must be implemented by all teachers, especially English teachers in serving their students and Application of reward and punishment for teachers in implementing teaching and learning standards in serving their students

Based on the test results, it can be explained that the implementation of the Subject Teacher Conference policy has no significant effect on the management of English learning in realizing the performance of English teachers. So from these calculations it is known that the implementation of the Subject Teacher Deliberative Policy policy does not significantly impact the management of English learning, which in itself will realize the performance of English teachers. With the existence of regulations governing the existence of teacher deliberations, the Government hopes that teachers who are involved in teacher deliberation programs, especially English teachers can always improve the management of English learning, in order to be able to manage education that is more dynamic, more productive teaching which in turn can have a satisfied effect on students, parents and society in

general as the targets of this public policy. In the opinion of the author, in the implementation of English learning management, continuous supervision is needed so that its implementation can be in accordance with existing standards. Because with the implementation of standardized English learning management, the English teacher's performance will get better. This is in line with and supported by research conducted by Anwar, R (2011) which reveals that the effectiveness of the implementation of teacher deliberation activities can increase the ability of teachers to teach so that the skills of a teacher can be improved. In line with that research conducted by Hermawati, W. (2017) reveals that the influence of motivation and group work in discussing subjects can improve a teacher's ability to master science and teach it. and is also supported by research conducted by Mulyawan, B. (2013) that there is an effect of experience in training on increasing teacher professional competence so that teachers can teach with increased knowledge.

Thus, this condition indicates that the management of English learning has no significant effect on the performance of English teachers. The better the management of English learning shown by the teacher, the better the performance of the given English teacher.

4. Conclusion

This research concluded that to realize the performance of English teachers can be done by optimizing the implementation of the subject teacher deliberation policy and management of English learning. coupled with improving the quality and creativity of the teacher so that learning English is expected to be fun and enjoyable

References

- Aisyah, R., Zakiyah, I. A., Farida, I., & Ramdhani, M. A. (2017). Learning Crude Oil by Using Scientific Literacy Comics. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 895(1), 012011.
- Amin, A. S., & Ramdhani, M. A. (2006). Konfigurasi Model untuk Sistem Pendukung Keputusan [Model Configuration for Decision Support Systems]. *Majalah Ilmiah Ekonomi Komputer*, 16(1), 11-19.
- Anwar, R. (2011). Pengaruh Musyawarah Guru Mata Pelajaran Terhadap Peningkatan Profesionalisme dan Kinerja Mengajar Guru SMA Negeri Kota Tasikmalaya [The Influence of Subject Teacher Deliberation on the Improvement of Professionalism and Teaching Performance of Tasikmalaya Public High School Teachers]. *Jurnal administrasi pendidikan*, 13(1).
- Casio, W. F. (2006). *Managing Human Resources: Productivity, Quality of Worklife and Profits*. Singapore: Mc.Graw Hill International.
- Helsy, I., Maryamah, Farida, I., & Ramdhani, M. A. (2017). Volta-Based Cells Materials Chemical Multiple Representation to Improve Ability of Student Representation. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 895(1), 012010.
- Hermawati, W. (2017). Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja Guru dan Implementasi Program Kerja Musyawarah Guru Mata Pelajaran Terhadap Kinerja Mengajar Guru di MTs Negeri Model Brebes [The Effect of Teacher Work Motivation and Implementation of Subject Teacher Deliberative Work Programs on Teacher Teaching Performance at State MTs Model Brebes]. *Syntax literate; jurnal ilmiah Indonesia*, 2(9), 170-193.
- Irwansyah, F. S., Lubab, I., & Ramdhani, I. F. (2017). Designing Interactive Electronic Module in Chemistry Lessons. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 895(1), 012009.
- Iskandar, J. (2015). *Metode Penelitian Administrasi [Administrative Research Methods]*. Bandung: Puspaga.
- Jalal, F. (2005). *Teachers' Quality Improvement in Indonesia: New Paradigm and Milestones*. Jakarta: Departemen Pendidikan Nasional.
- Mulyawan, B. (2013). Pengaruh Pengalaman Dalam Pelatihan Terhadap Peningkatan Kompetensi Profesional Guru [The Effect of Experience in Training on the Improvement of Teacher Professional Competence]. *Media Komunikasi FPIPS*, 11(1).
- Nurfajrinah, M. A., Nurhadi, Z. F., & Ramdhani, M. A. (2017). Meaning of Online Shopping for Indie Model. *The Social Sciences*, 12(4), 737-742.
- Nurlaeli, Y., & Saryono, O. (2018). Efektivitas Musyawarah Guru Mata Pelajaran dalam Meningkatkan Kinerja Mengajar Guru Bahasa Inggris [The Effectiveness of Subject Teacher Deliberations in Improving the Teaching Performance of English Teachers]. *Indonesian Journal Of Education Management & Administration Review* 2(2).
- Ramdhani, A., & Ramdhani, M. A. (2017). Konsep Umum Pelaksanaan Kebijakan Publik [General Concept of Public Policy Implementation]. *Jurnal Publik*, 11(1), 1-12.
- Ramdhani, M. A. (2013). *Metodologi Penelitian dalam Riset Teknologi Informasi [Research Methodology in Information Technology Research]*. Bandung: UIN Sunan Gunung Djati Bandung.

- Ramdhani, M. A. (2017). Lingkungan Pendidikan dalam Implementasi Pendidikan Karakter [Educational Environment in the Implementation of Character Education]. *Jurnal Pendidikan Universitas Garut*, 28-37.
- Ramdhani, M. A., & Muhammadiyah, H. (2015). The Criteria of Learning Media Selection for Character Education in Higher Education. *International Conference of Islamic Education in Southeast Asia* (pp. 174-182). Malang: UIN Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang.
- Ramdhani, M. A., & Ramdhani, A. (2016). *Penelitian Pemasaran [Marketing Research]*. Bandung: UIN Sunan Gunung Djati Bandung.
- Robbins, S. (2007). *Perilaku Organisasi [Organizational behavior]*. Jakarta: Prehalindo.
- Sari, S., Anjani, R., Farida, I., & Ramdhani, M. A. (2017). Using Android-Based Educational Game for Learning Colloid Material. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 895(1), 012012.
- Siagian, S. (2009). *Teori Motivasi dan Aplikasinya*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Spencer, L. M., & Spencer, S. M. (2003). *Competence at Work*. New York: John Willey & Sons.
- Stoner, J. A., & Freeman, R. E. (1989). *Management*. New Jersey: Prentice-Hall.
- Thohir, L., Zamzam, A., & Amin, M. (2019). Pengembangan Profesionalisme Guru Melalui Pelatihan Penulisan Karya Tulis Ilmiah Pada Bahasa Inggris [Development of Teacher Professionalism through Training on Writing Scientific Papers in English.]. *Jurnal Gema Ngabdi*
- Uno, H. B., & Lamatenggo, N. (2014). *Teori Kinerja dan Pengukurannya [Performance Theory and Its Measurement]*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
- Winarno, B. (2016). *Kebijakan Publik Era Globalisasi: Teori, Proses dan Studi Kasus Komparatif [Globalization Era Public Policy: Theory, Process and Comparative Case Studies]*. Yogyakarta: Center of Academic Publishing Service.